

EVALUATION OF INTRAPLY SHEAR IN THERMOFORMED COMPOSITE PRODUCTS

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the Square Grid Analysis for Thermoformed Composites (SGATC) technique and its evaluation process with the aim of investigating experimentally intraply shear deformations in several thermoformed thermoplastic composite products. The tool uses a laminate with an upper layer of hybrid carbon/glass fiber fabric with a plain weave used as a reference pattern. After forming, the deformed pattern is studied and the intraply shear is assessed. As a result, this procedure helps the designer to perform a quick identification of critical deformation areas, and it allows a calibration of the forming simulation tools. There is a notorious improvement in the accuracy of the shear angle measurements for curvature regions, and a considerable time reduction in the overall evaluation process. In addition, the tool can be used to compute the curvature radii of unbalanced laminates to estimate residual stresses on thermoplastic composite materials.

KEYWORDS: Intraply shear, thermoforming, drapability analysis, fiber orientation, square grid analysis, structural finite element analysis, residual stress.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic woven composites can rapidly be formed into components from raw materials using thermoforming processes. Most of these processes were derived from classical metal forming technologies and show, in general, the same principles [1]. However, in the design of new composites parts, it is necessary to have a good understanding of the behavior of the material through its manufacturing stage. During the thermoforming, the laminate is heated and deformed to meet the complex geometry of a mold. Among the most important deformation mechanisms involved, the intraply shear or Trellis effect is responsible for the formability of the laminate over the mold [2]. The shear deformation of woven fabrics is limited by the so-called locking angle; the smaller the locking angle, the better the deformation possibilities of the fabric. Excessive shearing angles imply manufacturing difficulties, the part could have thickness distributions and the fibers may not maintain the desired orientations. Therefore, the evaluation of intraply shear on real products during the R&D stage is a necessity in order to assess the mechanical behavior of the component and to reduce the time and development costs associated with the trial-and-error approach.

Conventional Measurement Techniques

There are several ways to estimate the shear deformation of thermoformed composites, where most of them rely on the use of a grid or a pattern attached to the surface of the part. Once the pattern deforms, the deformation can be measurement utilizing the available techniques like

manual, milling pointer, transducer and optical measurements. A brief outline of these techniques is presented here.

Manual Measurement: This method is the simplest to perform and it uses calibrated transparency tapes similar to Mylar tape in order to measure the angles of a rectangular deformed pattern. This technique allows quick measurements and there are not apparent geometrical restrictions like high steep walls. However, the poor precision (associated with the availability of pattern angles and the use of planar trigonometry), the number of values that can be measured, and the fact that it is a user dependent method limit the use of this technique.

Milling Pointer Measurement: In order to handle relatively large components, it is possible to use the digitizer of a milling machine. The pointer is localized over each deformed grid point and the milling machine controller creates a coordinate file. This method is a full-field measurement and additional post-processing is minimal [See Fig. 1A]. However, there are some disadvantages such as machine availability (very expensive), long time for measurement and low accuracy on very steep walls.

Transducer Measurement: The precision of the measurements can be improved if a X-Y table coupled with a vertical transducer is used. Thus, the X, Y and Z coordinates of every intersection point of the grid are obtained [See Fig. 1B]. The accuracy of this method is high (depending on the used transducer) and there is no problem with high steep walls. Nevertheless, the technique is limited to small components and it is a time consuming task.

Fig. 1: Some conventional measurement methods. A) Milling pointer measurement. B) Transducer measurement.

Optical Measurements: The experimental evaluation using the above-mentioned measurement techniques is not always easy. They are restricted on sample size and complexity. Thus, in a typical 3D thermoformed part with curvilinear geometry, many regions of interest must be measured. Therefore, a full-field technique is required, providing a feedback for the manufacturing simulations. In order to perform an automatic and full-field measurement, the optic methods offer a good solution, and several techniques could be used for the intraply

shear measurement. Thus, with the aim of evaluating the intraply shear phenomenon, a Square Grid Analysis (SGA) tool, adapted from the traditional metal applications, has been developed using Matlab® [3] and some of its applications and results are shown on this work.

SQUARE GRID ANALYSIS FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES (SGATC)

Description of the Measurement System

The SGA technique is a well-known experimental method used for strain analysis in metal forming processes, where an array with a good contrast is placed or attached to the sample prior to the deformation [5,6]. In contrast with metals, the composite thermoplastic matrix is molten due to the high process temperature, so the array will be subject to distortion. For that reason, it is unadvisable to use inks or any other kind of superficial marks. In order to visualize the deformations, the most suitable arrangement for woven composites is incorporating a weave pattern in the specimen using two kinds of fibers to improve the contrast like carbon and glass fibers. Thus, the SGATC tool uses a laminate with an upper layer of hybrid carbon/glass fiber fabric with a plain weave [3]. This layer is used as a reference pattern with a known geometry prior to forming.

After thermoforming, the user selects a region of interest in the piece to analyze, and takes a series of pictures of the product from different perspective views with a video or digital camera [See Fig. 2]. From the photos, the deformed array position is localized and with two or more images, the global 3D coordinates are computed using perspective projection geometry. Next, a stereo reconstruction is performed. The relationship between the global coordinate system and the pixel coordinate system is obtained by camera calibration using a known target. Finally, the global coordinates are used to compute the shearing angles for each deformed square.

Fig. 2: SGATC set-up

Perspective Projection

One way to describe the geometric aspect of an object that forms one image is using projective geometry and its perspective projections. The perspective is the projection of a 3D object onto a 2D surface by straight lines that pass through a single point. This point is called the *projection or camera center* C and it can be the origin of a 3D global coordinate system whose Z -axis is along the optical axis [See Fig. 3]. Now, if a point P on an object with global coordinates (X,Y,Z) is registered as p on some image plane at a *focal length* f from C , it will have the image coordinate (x,y) . The relationship between the two coordinate systems is given by:

$$x = \frac{Xf}{Z} \quad \text{and} \quad y = \frac{Yf}{Z} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3: Camera and Global coordinate systems

The use of homogeneous coordinates [7] can linearized the Eqn. 1, thus

$$\begin{bmatrix} sx \\ sy \\ s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & f & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where, s is a scale factor. In a digital image, the origin of the pixel coordinate system (u, v) is defined in the top left corner of the image plane and the relationships between both coordinate systems are the following:

$$u = u_c + \frac{x}{\text{pixel width}} \quad \text{and} \quad v = v_c + \frac{y}{\text{pixel height}} \quad (2)$$

In order to transform the 3D global coordinates into the pixel coordinates, it is necessary to use a 3x4 matrix, thus

$$\begin{bmatrix} su \\ sv \\ s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{f}{\text{pixel width}} & 0 & u_c & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{f}{\text{pixel height}} & v_c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The Eq.3 can be rewritten in matrix notation as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{M} \quad (4)$$

where:

$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ = Image pixel coordinate homogeneous vector

\mathbf{P} = 3x4 Perspective projection matrix

\mathbf{M} = Global coordinate homogeneous vector

The parameters f , pixel width, pixel height, u_c and v_c are the *intrinsic* camera parameters, and they do not depend on the position and orientation of the camera in space. In general, the 3D global coordinate system may not be aligned with the camera. Therefore, a modification in the Eqn. 4 must be included to take in account this case as follow

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{M} \quad (5)$$

where, \mathbf{K} is a 4x4 camera transformation matrix. Finally, the matrixes \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{K} can be written into a single 3x4 matrix \mathbf{C} called the *Camera Calibration Matrix*.

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} q_{11} & q_{12} & q_{13} & q_{14} \\ q_{21} & q_{22} & q_{23} & q_{24} \\ q_{31} & q_{32} & q_{33} & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Camera Calibration

The relationship between the global coordinates and the pixel (image) coordinates is obtained by camera calibration using a known object. On this paper, a steel cube with nine holes per face was used as target. Thus, the calibration matrix \mathbf{C} is obtained solving the Eqn. 6.

$$\mathbf{B} \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{UV} \quad (6)$$

Where, \mathbf{B} is a 2Nx11 matrix of constraint coefficients; \mathbf{C} is the unknown 11x1 calibration matrix, and \mathbf{UV} is a 2N image coordinate vector of the target points. If the matrix \mathbf{C} is known for each image, then any image point P with unknown X , Y , and Z coordinates, that projects onto the two image planes at (u,v) and (u',v') , will satisfy the Eqn. 7.

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} - uC_{31} & C_{12} - uC_{32} & C_{13} - uC_{33} \\ C_{21} - vC_{31} & C_{22} - vC_{32} & C_{23} - vC_{33} \\ C'_{11} - u'C_{31} & C'_{12} - u'C_{32} & C'_{13} - u'C_{33} \\ C'_{21} - v'C_{31} & C'_{22} - v'C_{32} & C'_{23} - v'C_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} uC_{34} - C_{14} \\ vC_{34} - C_{24} \\ u'C_{34} - C'_{14} \\ v'C_{34} - C'_{24} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Post-processing

Once Eqn. 7 has been solved, the 3D global coordinates can be calculated and used to compute the shearing angles. Then, the stereo reconstruction and the geometrical simulation, performed by Drape® [4], are compared using a matching process. This procedure allows a quick calibration of the simulation tool. Afterwards, the real fiber orientation distribution can be exported to commercial software like ABAQUS® computing structural finite element analysis. These simulations allow the designer to assess the variation in performance due to “alterations” introduced by the thermoforming manufacturing process. The experimental evaluation is also used as a feedback during the whole design process [Fig. 4].

Fig. 4: Experimental feedback during the R&D process for thermoformed composites

How the Software works

After a desired part has been thermoformed, it will be placed in the set-up shown on Fig. 2 with proper light conditions avoiding glare spots on the surfaces. Then, a dedicated Graphic User Interface starts an image acquisition procedure. This process can utilize a stream video camera via *firewire* port IEEE-1394 or a digital camera via USB port.

Fig. 5: SGATC software

Fig. 6: Two different pictures of the same object and the input image section.

At least two pictures of the same object are taken from two different perspective views. The higher the picture resolution, the lower the error in the computation. Both pictures must include the target and the same region of interest [See Fig. 6]. The image noise, light and atmospheric conditions can also affect the resulting image; hence, an image enhancement process will improve the quality of the images and can correct any defect on the grid pattern [See Fig. 7]. In addition, the pictures will be transformed first from color format (RGB) to gray scale, and then to binary in order to perform different morphological operations. The binary image is obtained by thresholding the gray level image; pixels with a gray level above the threshold are set to 1, whilst the rest are set to 0.

Fig. 7: Image enhancement process.

Once the pictures are in *good* condition, the calibration process is performed using the cubic target [See Fig. 8]. It is possible to increase the number of the calibration points improving the accuracy of the computations.

Fig. 8: Camera calibration process with a cubic target.

Then, the user selects various points of the region of interest over the shape as it is shown on Fig. 9. With the selected coordinates, a 3D stereo reconstruction is performed.

Fig. 9: Selection of the region of interest and stereo reconstruction

Using the global coordinates, the shearing angle for each square is calculated and visualized as shown on Fig. 10. Then, the deformed grid is compared with a drapability analysis. In this stage, it is possible to superimpose both results and compare visually and numerically the fidelity of the simulation versus the experimental test as it is depicted on Fig. 11.

Fig. 10: Postprocessing. Shearing angle visualization

Fig. 11: Matching process for the simulated and reconstructed shape

THERMOFORMED EVALUATION

Evaluation of large components

In order to study the capabilities of the SGATC, several products were thermoformed using a laminate with 4 plies of woven glass and one hybrid carbon/glass woven ply in a PA-6 polymer matrix. The grid spacing on the hybrid ply is 7.5mm and the carbon woven lines are 1.7mm width. The shapes analyzed are the following: a hemisphere, a welding mask, and a sport bicycle helmet.

The hemisphere: This shape has been clearly depicted on the last section. However, the drapability simulation is shown in Fig. 11, and it is compared against the SGATC reconstruction. It can be observed that the intraply shear angle is greater in the real product than in the ideal one [See the arrow on Fig. 11]. It means that the real product has a higher probability to wrinkle earlier than the predicted simulation. Nevertheless, the general shearing behavior is well described by the Drape model in this case.

The mask: As example of a part with a large number of measurement points, a welding mask has been manufactured as it is shown on Fig. 12. A section with 493 points was analyzed and its reconstruction is visualized on the right hand side. Wrinkles are easily detected on the reconstruction as a non-smooth surface region (e.g. sharp corner) in the base [See arrow on Fig. 12]. This criterion can be used for an automatic quality inspection of thermoformed composite products.

The helmet: A thermoformed cycling helmet is observed on Fig. 13. In this case, a coarse grid hybrid layer was used (spacing of 26mm). As can be expected, the size of this grid affects the detail level or resolution and the accuracy of the measurement. As in the mask case, a strong non-smooth surface is distinguished on the lower part of the product. However, some of these faults fall outside the product and in some cases, a high shearing angle or wrinkling level is allowed by the designer.

Fig. 12: Evaluation of intraply shear on a thermoformed-welding mask

Fig. 13: Evaluation of a sport bicycle helmet.

Measurement of Curvature Radius for Residual Stress Estimation

In addition, the SGATC can be used to determine the curvature radius of unbalanced laminates with the aim of studying the residual stresses in thermoplastic composites [See Figs. 2 and 14]. Once the global coordinates are found, a circle fitting least-square procedure is used and the curvature radii are computed. More details about this investigation are presented by [8].

Fig. 14: Unbalanced composite laminate and the least-square fitting circle.

CONCLUSIONS

A computer-based full-field method has been developed and implemented using the Square Grid Analysis technique to study experimentally the intraply shear deformation of thermoformed thermoplastic composite parts. The SGATC software helps the designer in the identification of critical deformation areas and reduces considerably the time required to evaluate a thermoformed component. The system can be used for small or large parts; the only limitation relies on the availability of the hybrid pattern ply. Finally, the tool can be integrated easily in a concurrent manufacturing and design environment for composite materials and it allows a quick verification of numerical calculations.

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